

Exploiting 6G RAN and Core Network Information for Intelligent Edge-Cloud Service Orchestration

Michail Dalgitsis*, Godfrey M. Kibalya*, Maria A. Serrano*, Jordi Serra†, and Angelos Antonopoulos*

*Nearby Computing, Barcelona, Spain

†Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), Barcelona, Spain

Abstract—The advent of 5G networks and the imminent evolution to 6G have driven significant changes in mobile network architecture, emphasizing edge-cloud integration, network softwarization, and Application Programmable Interface (API)-driven service delivery. To optimize resource allocation, service scaling, and service migration, mobile network operators must leverage both Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN) information in orchestration frameworks. This paper introduces a novel cloud-native orchestration framework designed for 5G/6G networks, incorporating RAN and CN data to enable dynamic and efficient management of edge services. The framework includes three key orchestration strategies: (i) Horizontal Service Instance Autoscaler (HSIA), which adjusts service availability based on the number of active users derived from core network session data; (ii) Horizontal Service Resource Autoscaler (HSRA), which scales resources based on aggregated radio traffic from base stations; and (iii) Horizontal Service Edge-Cloud Migration (HSECM), which dynamically migrates services to the cloud when edge resources are insufficient. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of these strategies in reducing energy consumption and minimizing users affected by service migration (UASM) while maintaining service quality. The findings highlight the transformative potential of mobile network-aware orchestration for enabling more sustainable and adaptive edge service deployments in next-generation networks.

Index Terms—Autoscaling, Edge Computing, Orchestration, Network-aware Orchestration, Network Exposure.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of 5G networks has transformed the traditional mobile network paradigm into a telco edge-cloud continuum by integrating network functions and edge-cloud applications. This shift, driven by softwarization, virtualization, and cloudification, optimizes 5G investments through efficient scaling and migration of network functions and applications [1]. Towards 6G networks, Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) are able to digitalize their service portfolios and offer them to verticals via initiatives like CAMARA and GSMA Open Gateway (OGW) [2]. These initiatives aim to monetize 5G/6G by providing new service layers for application developers, facilitated by network information exposure through standardized frameworks like 3GPP’s Northbound Framework [3], and ETSI Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) Platform [4].

An orchestration platform that manages and automates network functions and edge-cloud applications is key to this transformation. Yet, existing solutions fail to fully exploit real-time insights from the Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN) for efficient service scaling and migration. Several studies explore network-aware orchestration

using infrastructure-layer metrics, such as link capacity and inter-node delays, to optimize application placement and workload distribution [5]–[7]. While effective, these approaches overlook dynamic mobile network insights that could further enhance decision-making. Beyond infrastructure metrics, RAN and CN data offer additional orchestration opportunities. Some studies leverage mobile network information but focus on specific network operations [8]–[10] or application optimizations [11]–[14], rather than holistic service orchestration. By incorporating mobile network information, operators can make informed decisions about resource allocation, service scaling, and migration, enhancing user experience, optimizing network utilization, and reducing energy consumption. In this context, [15] incorporates mobile network information for scaling purposes. However, this work is limited to network function scaling and does not address edge-cloud applications.

In this paper, we introduce a novel approach to cloud-native edge service¹ orchestration framework, called *Network-aware Service Orchestration (NASO)*, designed for 5G/6G networks. In particular, our contribution is threefold:

- 1) We propose the NASO framework that integrates 6G RAN and core network information for efficient service management.
- 2) We design three strategies that are integrated in NASO:
 - Horizontal Service Instance Autoscaler (HSIA) for service availability based on active users.
 - Horizontal Service Resource Autoscaler (HSRA) for resource scaling based on radio traffic.
 - Horizontal Service Edge-Cloud Migration (HSECM) for dynamic service migrations.
- 3) We provide a performance evaluation for use cases focused on different metrics (i.e., energy and service migration impact) to demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II overviews network exposure in 5G/6G and service orchestration. Section III outlines the proposed system architecture. Section IV details the proposed orchestration strategies. Section V presents implementation details and experimental results. Section VI concludes the paper and discusses future research directions.

¹In this paper, “service” and “application” are used interchangeably. The term “service” refers to the orchestrator’s perspective when deploying an application manifest.

Fig. 1: Network exposure in 5G

II. NETWORK EXPOSURE AND SERVICE ORCHESTRATION

This section explores network exposure mechanisms and the orchestration platform’s role in optimizing service delivery and user experience. Focusing on the 5G/6G network exposure model, we highlight how network data is made accessible to applications and used for dynamic service management in next-generation networks.

A. Network Exposure by Network Apification

Network exposure allows external applications to access key network data, including RAN metrics (e.g., signal strength, user location) and CN information (e.g., latency, throughput). Previously reliant on vendor-specific solutions, 5G’s software-based architectures and monetization goals have standardized network Application Programmable Interfaces (APIs)—a process called network apification. These APIs ensure consistent access to network data, enabling resource optimization and responsive, network-aware applications.

Figure 1 illustrates the 5G network exposure model, divided into three layers:

Network Layer: The foundation comprises RAN and CN components. The RAN includes traditional RAN functions and Open-RAN (O-RAN) functions, while the CN encompasses the User Plane Function (UPF) and control plane elements like the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), Session Management Function (SMF), Network Repository Function (NRF), etc.

Network APIs Layer: APIs provide domain-specific access. RAN APIs are available via MEC services (e.g., Radio Network Information Service, Location Service) or via xApps and rApps, supported by O-RAN’s Real-time Intelligent Controller (RIC). CN APIs are exposed through the Network Exposure Function (NEF) [16] and Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) [10]. NEF ensures secure API access, while NWDAF offers advanced analytics. Abstraction frameworks like CAMARA and OGW simplify 3GPP-specific APIs, defining Service APIs on top of the already specified network APIs (offering the network APIs as-a-service), while

Fig. 2: Service orchestrator role in network exposure

the Common API Framework (CAPIF) bridges NEF and CAMARA for improved interoperability [17].

Network Consumers Layer: RAN consumers include xApps, rApps, and MEC applications. In the CN, NEF and NWDAF APIs are used by Application Functions (AFs). CAMARA APIs simplify access to 5G capabilities for vertical developers, offering a user-friendly interface.

This layered structure clarifies the interaction between network components, APIs, and consumers, illustrating how advanced 5G capabilities are exposed and utilized.

B. Role of Service Orchestration in Network Exposure

A service orchestration system plays a crucial role within the network exposure model, enhancing the process in three distinct ways:

i. **Network Consumer:** The orchestrator can act as a consumer of network APIs, querying mobile network data to perform network-aware orchestration actions. By leveraging real-time network information, the orchestrator can make informed decisions to optimize resource allocation and improve service delivery.

ii. **Network API Platform:** The orchestrator can serve as a platform that hosts all available network APIs for their consumers. In this role, the orchestrator exposes a centralized interface for accessing network APIs, facilitating seamless integration and interoperability among various application consumers.

iii. **Hybrid Role:** The orchestrator can adopt a hybrid role, functioning both as an API consumer and an API platform. This dual capability allows the orchestrator to not only utilize network data for its own operations but also to provide network information to other application consumers.

Figure 2 illustrates these three roles of a service orchestrator in the network exposure model. The figure highlights how an orchestrator interacts with network APIs and external applications, showcasing its versatility in managing and exposing network data.

Fig. 3: System architecture

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed system architecture consists of M regions, each served by an edge server that has a specific maximum CPU capacity, and N applications, whose manifests are initially onboarded on the service orchestration platform and dynamically deployed across these regions based on user demand. Users interact with applications within their respective regions, generating traffic and influencing the number of replicas required to meet service demands. In this work, the orchestration platform assumes the role of a network API consumer, leveraging real-time network data to enable informed decisions for application scaling and deployment.

The set of regions is denoted as $M = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M\}$, where each region r_i is served by a specific edge node from the set $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_M\}$ where e_i represents the edge node associated with region r_i and has a corresponding maximum CPU capacity C_{\max, r_i} , which varies across regions. The set of applications is denoted as $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N\}$, where each a_j represents an application in the system. The users in each region interact with these applications.

Each region r hosts a set of users U_r , denoted as $U_r = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{|U_r|}\}$, where $|U_r|$ denotes the number of users in region r . These users access applications from the total set $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N\}$, with the subset of active applications in region r denoted as $A_r \subseteq A$. The traffic generated by users accessing these applications is a key factor in determining the number of replicas required for each application in every region.

The total traffic for application a_j in region r_i , denoted as T_{r_i, a_j} , depends on the interactions of users in that region. Each user in region r_i generates traffic based on their interaction with an application a_j . The user demand in Mbps, denoted as D_u , contributes to the total traffic T_{r_i, a_j} , which determines the number of replicas required. The number of replicas R_{r_i, a_j} required to handle the traffic for application a_j in region r_i is calculated as:

$$R_{r_i, a_j} = \left\lceil \frac{T_{r_i, a_j}}{T_{a_j, \text{opt}}} \right\rceil \quad (1)$$

where $T_{a_j, \text{opt}}$ represents the optimal traffic-handling capacity of a single replica.

The CPU usage of a region is determined by the deployed replicas and their resource requirements. For region r_i , the total CPU usage C_{r_i} is given by:

$$C_{r_i} = \sum_{a_j \in A_r} R_{r_i, a_j} \cdot C_{a_j} \quad (2)$$

where C_{a_j} is the CPU requirement per replica of application a_j . The system verifies that the total CPU usage does not exceed the maximum capacity of the edge server in region r_i , by migrating an application a_j , ensuring that $C_{r_i} \leq C_{\max, r_i}$.

We evaluate energy consumption and the number of users affected by service migrations (UASM) for system validation, as they are critical to the efficiency and practicality of edge-cloud orchestration. Energy consumption reflects the system's sustainability and operational costs, highlighting its ability to minimize resource usage while maintaining performance. The number of UASM measures the impact of service relocations on user experience, such as increased latency or service interruptions, affecting quality of service (QoS). Together, these metrics provide a comprehensive view of the system's performance, balancing resource efficiency with user impact, and enabling comparisons with alternative strategies.

The energy consumption is calculated by considering both static and dynamic power components. The static power P_{static} represents the baseline power consumption of an edge server when at least one application is deployed, while the dynamic power P_{dynamic} scales with the actual CPU usage. The energy consumed (expressed in joules) by region r_i over a time interval T_{int} is given by:

$$E_{r_i} = (P_{\text{static}} + C_{r_i} \cdot P_{\text{dynamic}}) \cdot T_{\text{int}} \quad (3)$$

Application migrations occur when the maximum capacity of an edge node cannot accommodate all applications due to high user traffic, requiring one or more applications to be offloaded to the cloud. This migration directly impacts the users associated with the migrated applications in a region. Instead of computing a general "migration cost," we quantify the total number of UASM for region r per unit time as:

$$N_{\text{UASM}, r} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{window}}} \sum_{t=1}^{N_{\text{window}}} \sum_{u \in U_r} x_{u, t} \quad (4)$$

where:

- N_{window} is the total number of observation windows.

- $x_{u,t}$ is a binary variable indicating whether user u is affected by a migration during observation window t , with $x_{u,t} = 1$ if the application used by u is migrated, and $x_{u,t} = 0$ otherwise.

The total UASM N_{UASM_r} is normalized by the number of observation windows (N_{window}), representing the average number of UASM per region. This approach ensures consistency in measuring and comparing migration impact across regions and different system configurations.

IV. NETWORK-AWARE SERVICE ORCHESTRATION FRAMEWORK

To optimize resource utilization and energy efficiency in the telco edge-cloud environment, we propose three core mechanisms: **Horizontal Service Instance Autoscaler (HSIA)**, **Horizontal Service Resource Autoscaler (HSRA)**, and **Horizontal Service Edge-Cloud Migration (HSECM)**. These mechanisms dynamically manage service availability, resource allocation, and migration by leveraging real-time network information.

The **HSIA** ensures service availability on the orchestrated edge infrastructure by deploying or undeploying applications based on user activity, leveraging insights from the CN. Although the number of active users cannot be directly obtained from a network API, this information is derived by combining data from the application backend (tracking incoming and active user requests) and the SMF, which provides details on active user sessions. By processing and filtering this data, the orchestrator identifies mobile users connected via the RAN and makes deployment decisions accordingly, conserving resources in regions with no active users.

The **HSRA** dynamically adjusts application replicas within a single edge node based on real-time traffic conditions, leveraging metrics derived from the RAN, such as the aggregated radio traffic from associated base stations. This mechanism determines the optimal number of replicas needed to handle the traffic load efficiently. The orchestrator then scales the resources of a service up or down by adding or removing replicas—e.g., deploying or terminating additional pods in a Kubernetes-based environment—ensuring efficient resource usage without compromising service quality.

In contrast to the HSIA, which scales services across edge nodes by deploying or undeploying applications based on user activity in different regions, the HSRA operates within a single edge node, focusing on scaling horizontally in replicas. While the HSIA ensures that applications are distributed where needed, the HSRA fine-tunes the resource allocation for deployed applications to adapt to fluctuations in traffic.

The **HSECM** addresses resource shortages by dynamically managing the migration of services between edge and cloud nodes. It continuously monitors edge node resource utilization and determines which services to migrate based on the number of active users and their associated traffic. Specifically, if an application consumes significant CPU resources due to high radio traffic, it will be considered for migration unless it serves a large number of users. In such cases, the application

with fewer users but higher per-user traffic will be prioritized for migration to minimize the overall impact on users. This approach redistributes the load effectively, ensuring system performance and stability while reducing service disruptions.

Algorithm 1 NASO Algorithm

```

1: Input: SLAs (optimal traffic, CPU), edge nodes
2: Output: Selected edge nodes and/or cloud node
3: for each edge node  $e_i$  do
4:   for each application  $a_j$  assigned to  $e_i$  do
5:     if Active users for  $a_j > 0$  and  $a_j$  not running then
6:       Deploy  $a_j$  (HSIA)
7:     else if No active users and  $a_j$  is running then
8:       Undeploy  $a_j$ 
9:     end if
10:    if  $a_j$  is running then
11:      Calculate traffic  $T_{e_i, a_j}$  and replicas  $R_{e_i, a_j} =$ 
12:       $\lceil T_{e_i, a_j} / T_{a_j, \text{opt}} \rceil$ 
13:      if  $R_{e_i, a_j} \neq$  Current replicas then
14:        Scale  $a_j$  (HSRA)
15:      end if
16:    end for
17:    Calculate total CPU usage  $C_{e_i}$ 
18:    if  $C_{e_i} > C_{\text{max}, e_i}$  then
19:      Enable HSECM functionality
20:      Sort running applications by users served (ascending) and CPU requirements (descending)
21:      for each  $a_j$  in sorted list do
22:        Migrate  $a_j$  to cloud; update  $C_{e_i}$ 
23:        if  $C_{e_i} \leq C_{\text{max}, e_i}$  then Break
24:        end if
25:      end for
26:    end if
27: end for

```

These three mechanisms are implemented within the unified orchestration algorithm, as detailed in Algorithm 1. The algorithm efficiently combines the functionalities of HSIA, HSRA, and HSECM to manage application scaling and resource allocation dynamically.

The orchestration algorithm begins with the application owner specifying Service Level Agreements (SLAs), which define parameters such as the optimal traffic per replica, the application can handle without QoS degradation, the necessary compute resources (CPU cores), and the target available edge nodes. For each of the available edge nodes, the orchestrator first checks the number of active users. If active users are present and the application is not running, the orchestrator deploys the application (HSIA). If the application is already running, no action is taken. Conversely, if no active users are detected, the orchestrator undeploys the application to conserve resources. When an application is active, the algorithm calculates the aggregated radio traffic from base stations in the region. It determines the required number of replicas by dividing the current traffic by the optimal traffic per replica

and rounding the result. The orchestrator adjusts the number of replicas accordingly, scaling up when traffic increases and scaling down when traffic decreases (HSRA). This ensures efficient resource allocation while maintaining performance. Additionally, when resource shortages occur on edge nodes, the orchestrator invokes the HSECM functionality to migrate services to cloud nodes, redistributing the load and preserving system performance. To optimize the migration process, applications are first sorted by the number of active users in ascending order. If multiple applications have the same number of users, they are then sorted by CPU usage in descending order.

The complexity of the orchestration algorithm is determined by its nested loops over edge nodes and applications. For M edge nodes and N applications, the worst-case time complexity is $O(M \cdot N)$, with additional overhead for sorting applications during resource shortages ($O(N \log N)$). This ensures scalability for practical deployments with moderate M and N .

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The simulation settings, benchmark algorithms, and performance evaluation of NASO are discussed in this section.

A. Simulation Settings

The simulation evaluates two use cases: (i) Energy Consumption (EC) leveraging the HSIA and HSRA mechanism and (ii) Service Migration (SM) leveraging the HSECM mechanism. We assume a network topology (similar to our system architecture in Fig. 1) with varying number of regions (edge servers) and applications. The CPU capacity of each region, the CPU requirement of each application, and traffic threshold per application replica follow a uniform distribution. A series of simulated events represents user behavior, where the number of users per region and the applications they use are randomized. For each event, the traffic generated by users is calculated and translated into application replicas to meet demand, subject to resource constraints. Table I summarizes the simulation parameters, where “EC” denotes parameters relevant to the Energy Consumption use case, “SM” denotes those used in the Service Migration use case, and parameters marked with “both” are shared across both scenarios. Note that $U(x, y)$ in the table denotes the uniform distribution between x and y .

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters

Param.	Description	Use Case	Values
N	Applications	EC, SM	[1, 50], 10
M	Regions (edge nodes)	EC, SM	[2, 50], 1
C_{\max, r_i}	Max CPU per region r_i	EC, SM	U(4, 16), 16
C_{a_j}	CPU/replica of a_j	Both	U(1, 3)
$T_{a_j, \text{opt}}$	Opt. traffic/replica (Mbps)	Both	U(50, 500)
D_u	User demand (Mbps)	Both	U(2, 20)
$ U_r $	Users per region r	EC, SM	U(10, 50), [10, 400]
$ A_r $	Apps per edge node	EC, SM	U(0, N-1), N
N_{window}	Simulation events	Both	1000
P_{dynamic}	Dyn. power (W)	EC	0.5
P_{static}	Static power (W)	EC	10
T_{int}	Time interval (s)	EC	3600

B. Benchmark Algorithms

For the energy consumption use case, the baseline algorithm, referred to as *Full-Deployment*, deploys all applications across all available edge nodes, regardless of user presence. For the service migration use case, three baseline algorithms were employed: *Random-SM*, which migrates applications randomly without considering CPU or user metrics; *CPU-based-High-SM*, which migrates applications with the highest CPU consumption to minimize the number of migrations, though it does not account for user impact; and *CPU-based-Low-SM*, which migrates applications with the lowest CPU consumption, assuming that lower CPU consumption is associated with lower radio traffic and thus fewer affected users.

C. Simulation Results and Discussion

The results first demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed dynamic network-aware deployment strategy in significantly reducing energy consumption compared to the Full-Deployment approach. Heatmap visualizations in Fig. 4 illustrate the average energy consumption across various configurations of M regions and N applications, highlighting the scalability and adaptability of the proposed strategy. Unlike the Full-Deployment strategy, which statically deploys all applications regardless of actual demand and consistently consumes more energy, NASO selectively deploys applications based on user activity. This dynamic strategy achieves energy reduction percentages that grow with the number of applications and regions, reaching over 50% in high-demand scenarios. Additionally, it maintains service quality while reducing the frequency of CPU utilization exceeding regional capacity, demonstrating better resource efficiency. These findings emphasize the potential of dynamic application scaling in edge computing environments, especially for systems with highly variable user demand.

However, edge nodes often face resource constraints, making it challenging to accommodate all applications and their replicas when CPU capacity is exceeded. To address this, our approach focuses on migrating selected services to the cloud while minimizing user impact. As shown in Fig. 5, the choice of migration strategy significantly affects system performance, with affected user percentages varying across scenarios. Our results indicate that NASO consistently outperform others, particularly in high-traffic conditions. For applications with an optimal handling capacity $T_{a, \text{opt}}$ of 500 Mb/s per replica, NASO maintains the lowest affected percentage (around 17–18%) even as the system scales. In contrast, Random-SM and CPU-based-Low-SM lead to significantly higher user impact, exceeding 80% in the most constrained cases. CPU-based-High-SM offers moderate improvements but still results in over 30% affected users under high loads. Additionally, a higher per-replica capacity (500 Mb/s vs. 100 Mb/s) reduces user impact across all strategies, confirming that application overload, is a key factor in performance degradation, since with a higher per-replica capacity, fewer replicas are required, reducing the number of migrations needed and further improving system stability. These findings highlight the importance of

Fig. 4: Energy consumption

Fig. 5: Affected users due to service migration

intelligent, network-aware migration strategies in edge-cloud architectures to optimize resource utilization while preserving system stability and user experience.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented NASO, a novel orchestration framework for 5G/6G networks that integrates insights from both the RAN and CN to dynamically manage edge service scaling and migration. By introducing three key deployment and scaling functionalities (i.e., HSIA, HSRA, and HSECM), we

have demonstrated significant improvements in energy efficiency and reduced UASM compared to network-unaware approaches. Future work will focus on implementing the proposed framework using cloud-native tools and deploying it on real telco edge-cloud infrastructure. This will allow for more practical validation and refinement of the framework, enabling its application in real-world network environments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the Horizon Europe SNS JU UNITY-6G project funded by the European Commission (ID 101192650) as well as the 6G-OASIS (TSI-063000-2021-24) project from the UNICO5G-RPTR programme.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Boutouchent *et al.*, "AMANOS: An Intent-Driven Management and Orchestration System for Next-Generation Cloud-Native Networks," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 62, no. 6, pp. 42–49, 2024.
- [2] R. Kurdman *et al.*, "MEC Federation for Seamless Service Continuity in Cross-Border Mobility Scenarios," in *IEEE VTC2024-Fall*, Oct 2024, accepted for publication.
- [3] 3GPP, "System architecture for the 5G System (5GS)," Technical Specification 23.501 V19.2.1, January 2025.
- [4] ETSI, "MEC support towards Edge Native Design," White Paper No. 55, June 2023.
- [5] J. Santos *et al.*, "Diktyo: Network-Aware Scheduling in Container-Based Clouds," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 4461–4477, 2023.
- [6] K. Govindarajan, C. Govindarajan, and M. Verma, "Network Aware Container Orchestration for Telco Workloads," in *2022 IEEE 15th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD)*, 2022, pp. 397–406.
- [7] A. Marchese and O. Tomarchio, "Network-Aware Container Placement in Cloud-Edge Kubernetes Clusters," in *2022 22nd IEEE International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Internet Computing (CCGrid)*, 2022, pp. 859–865.
- [8] V.-M. Alevizaki *et al.*, "Distributed Service Provisioning for Disaggregated 6G Network Infrastructures," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 120–137, 2023.
- [9] R. A. Addad *et al.*, "AI-Based Network-Aware Service Function Chain Migration in 5G and Beyond Networks," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 472–484, 2022.
- [10] P. K. Gkonis *et al.*, "Leveraging Network Data Analytics Function and Machine Learning for Data Collection, Resource Optimization, Security and Privacy in 6G Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 21 320–21 336, 2024.
- [11] N. Nikaein, X. Vasilakos, and A. Huang, "LL-MEC: Enabling Low Latency Edge Applications," in *2018 IEEE 7th International Conference on Cloud Networking (CloudNet)*, 2018, pp. 1–7.
- [12] W. Nakimuli *et al.*, "Exploiting radio access information to improve performance of remote-controlled mobile robots in MEC-based 5G networks," *Computer Networks*, vol. 212, p. 109061, 2022.
- [13] N. Li *et al.*, "Transforming the 5G RAN With Innovation: The Confluence of Cloud Native and Intelligence," vol. 11, 2023, pp. 4443–4454.
- [14] M. A. Hathibelagal, R. G. Garoppo, and G. Nencioni, "Experimental comparison of migration strategies for MEC-assisted 5G-V2X applications," *Computer Communications*, vol. 197, pp. 1–11, 2023.
- [15] A. Mudvari, N. Makris, and L. Tassiulas, "ML-driven scaling of 5G Cloud-Native RANs," in *2021 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [16] G. Makropoulos *et al.*, "5G and B5G NEF exposure capabilities towards an Industrial IoT use case," in *2023 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, 2023, pp. 647–651.
- [17] J. Fernandes *et al.*, "Pushing the Boundaries of Scalable 5G Core Networks: Cloud-Native NEF and CAPIF Interplay," in *2024 3rd International Conference on 6G Networking (6GNet)*, 2024, pp. 201–205.